

Plaaslik ontwikkelde basterpampoen nou werklikheid

Die nuwe baster-boerpampoen **STAR 7001** het groot belangstelling uitgelok tydens Starke Ayres se Groente Boeredag wat in Februarie 1994 by die Pannar Navorsingstasie naby Delmas gehou is.

Nagenoeg 300 boere van alle dele van die land het die suksesvolle boeredag, wat oor twee dae aangebied was, bygewoon. Besoekers is in groepe van ongeveer dertig, op begeleide toere deur die demonstrasiepersele geneem, waar hulle die geleentheid gehad het om 'n aantal nuwe kultivars van verskeie gewasse te besigtig soos hulle skouer aan skouer langs die oewer, gevestigde kultivars gestaan het.

STAR 7001 het veral beïndruk vanwee sy hoër en meer bestendige opbrengste, verbeterde kwaliteit en vinnige rypwording.

Volgens Mnr. Errol Bosch, Starke

STAR 7001 met sy tipiese diep-oranje kleur en dik vleis, veral by die blom-end letsel.

STAR 7001 vertoon 'n tipiese bosagtige groeiwyse wat onkruidbeheer vergemaklik en verbeterde benutting van voedingstowwe bevorder.

Ayres se Navorsingsbeampte wat grootliks verantwoordelik was vir die ontwikkeling van **STAR 7001**, produseer hierdie kultivar vrugte soortgelyk aan die van Plat Wit Boer "A" dit wil sê, ongeveer 4 kg of selfs groter.

"**STAR 7001** produseer egter tot 10% meer vrugte per plant en omdat die plantestand met bykans 27% tot 7 000 plante per ha opgestoot kan word as gevolg van sy meer bosagtige groeiwyse, kan 'n totale opbrengsverhoging van tot 30% en selfs hoër behaal word." Die kultivar se bosagtige groeiwyse vergemaklik ook meganiese onkruidbeheer, wat die plante in staat stel om voedingstowwe beter te benut en nog groter opbrengste te lewer.

Nog 'n groot voordeel van **STAR 7001** is sy hitteverdraagsaamheid: — "In teenstelling met ander boerpampoene produseer **STAR 7001** voldoende vroulike blomme onder warm toestande. Met normale boerpampoenkultivars, kan totale

oesmislukkings plaasvind weens 'n gebrek aan die vorming van vroulike blomme tydens baie warm weer, soos in Desember and Januarie. Die gevolg is dat dit nie net hoër en meer bestendige opbrengste lewer nie, maar dwarsdeur die somer aangeplant kan word."

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(from page 1)

Volgens Mnr. Bosch kan die feit dat **STAR 7001** ongeveer drie weke vinniger as ander soortgelyke boerpampoene ryp word, ook groot voordele vir die produsent inhou. Besproeiing- en spuitkoste is minder, die land kan vinniger vrygestel word vir die volgende gewas, en daar is groter

aanpasbaarheid wat plantdatum en bemaking betref. Vrugte is ook gouer beskikbaar met aanplanting na die winter.

"Vir die verbruiker is van belang dat die vrugte van **STAR 7001** 'n goeie rակlewe en 'n baie klein blom-end letsel het. Die dieporanje gekleurde vleis is dikker in die middel van die pampoene en van 'n besonder hoë gehalte wat nie

net verseker dat die produsent 'n beter prys vir sy produk kry nie, maar ook die verbruiker meer waarde vir sy geld gee", aldus Mnr. Bosch.

Beperkte saadvoorrade van **STAR 7001** is vir die komende seisoen beskikbaar. Aangesien daar verwag word dat die aanvraag groot sal wees, word produsente aangeraai om hul saadbestelling so gou moontlik te plaas.

Flower Extravaganza

The Garden at the Pannar Research Station in Delmas was again the venue for the 1994 Starke Ayres Flower Extravaganza.

Thousands of seedlings were produced, planted and nurtured for the occasion. They were in full bloom for a number of weeks and during this time many people visited the striking display of mass colour.

Members of the bedding plant industry visited the Extravaganza on 27th January when many ideas, new products and marketing strategies were discussed. Many nursery managers welcome the opportunity of bringing their sales staff to show them how to use colour in the garden and how to assist the public when it comes to using bedding plants.

Besides the representatives from the industry, many garden clubs, members of the public, farmers wives, and interested persons also visited the display. For them, the Starke Ayres staff were on hand with demonstrations on planting hanging baskets, tips on gardening with colour and any information on using bedding plants. These proved to be very stimulating and informative workshops.

The colourful plantings of the new large-flowering **Pride Impatiens** and the new colours of **Phlox Dolly** attracted a

Phlox Dolly is now also available in separate colours of burgundy, deep rose, purple and white.

lot of attention, as did the new **Grandiflora Eagle Series** of Petunia.

The display of Impatiens was outstanding and the 'colour pillars' were the centre of attraction. They received many complimentary remarks. This planting, which was in full sun served to display the versatility of **Impact Impatiens**. Only **Impact**

Impatiens can be used in situations such as this as they have the unique heat resisting quality seldom seen in other Impatiens.

Impact Impatiens in a garden setting with 'colour pillars' in the background.

Part of the Starke Ayres Display Garden at Delmas. Portulaca Sundial is in the foreground.

Editor's View

Marketing is unfortunately frequently thought to be simply a fancy word for advertising. While advertising is indeed a high profile aspect of marketing, the concept of marketing involves virtually every aspect of business activity. Too few farmers and nurserymen observe the overall impact which their actions have on their businesses.

An obvious aspect of marketing would be the concept of a brand. This might be as simple as using the business name on the packaging. Carrots and punnets of bedding plants come to mind as relevant examples. A

brand name is a means of reinforcing the image of the company, and therefore also enhancing product value.

Marketing does not stop with simply the image of the business to its customers. What about the suppliers and staff? Suppliers must consider credit-worthiness and the ability to use their products correctly, particularly products requiring a high degree of technical expertise. The staff should be willing and able to project the desired image of the business.

I am not recommending that farm offices be padded out to look grand, or gilt-edged business cards be used simply to mislead potential customers. Marketing should be an honest appraisal and deliberate use of the best aspects of your business, as well as a means of improving those areas which require improvement. Every business, regardless of size, needs to have a positive and successful marketing drive. Look carefully at all aspects and consider the image it creates of your business to customers, suppliers and staff.

This will be my last issue of *Seedling News*. I have accepted a position with Lannen Plant Systems of Christchurch, New Zealand. I wish to thank my colleagues in Starke Ayres, as well as customers and others in all aspects of horticulture, for the helpful and pleasant business environment which I have enjoyed. I wish you all everything of the best for the future.

SEEDLING NEWS

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Die koste verbonde aan die plasing van artikels in beide Engels en Afrikaans is ontsaglik duur. Lesers wat 'n vertaling van enige artikel benodig is egter welkom om daarvoor aan te vra. Stuur 'n self-geadresseerde koevert met die nodige posseëls aan ons en dui duidelik aan watter artikel u benodig.

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Waterlogging and germination

by Warrick Nelson

Waterlogging the growing medium has a marked effect on the rate of cabbage seedling emergence. Significant differences were recorded after seven days from sowing.

Investigating seedling problems involves trying to deduce what might have caused a problem, long after other evidence of the cause is gone. A spate of germination problems in seed lots testing good under the ISTA rules suggested something was reducing effective germination at some nurseries. What was particularly baffling was that some nurseries continued having excellent germination results throughout the whole period, and with the same seed lots.

After much head-scratching, I wondered whether the long period of drizzly, misty weather occurring at the time was related to the problem. I then began noting which nurseries reported germination problems and linked this with where they placed trays during the critical early germination period.

Almost without exception, where germination problems were reported, sown trays were placed out in the nursery either directly after, or within a day of sowing. Comparing roots of seedlings from trays exhibiting poor emergence with the occasional tray in the nursery showing good emergence showed "onion-root" growth typical under waterlogged conditions.

Some months later I decided to check the assumption that waterlogging could seriously affect germination. I sowed cabbage seed into Speedling trays and counted emerged seedlings after seven days. Half the trays were watered once after sowing, the other half were floated on water to ensure constant saturation of the composted pine bark growing medium. The differences between treatments are highly significant. Results of three replications are shown in the graph.

Of particular importance is to note that by the time poor emergence is recorded, other evidence of the cause of poor emergence is highly unlikely to still be present.

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Besigheid bv. — bosbou, groenteboer, saailing kweker ens.

Snippets

Virus infection of cucurbits and solanaceous crops can seriously reduce yields and yield quality. Some varieties are being bred with a silver mottling on the leaves, particularly common in newer varieties of zucchini. Research conducted in Israel has resulted in the discovery that aphids, the major cause of the spread of virus infections into new crops, become confused when flying over silver/grey mottled surfaces. This confusion reduces the chances that the aphid will settle and feed on the crop, thus reducing the chances of virus infection. Silver/grey mulches or blobs of whitewash on the leaves have a similar effect where natural colouring in the leaf is not available.

High-sugar sweetcorns, particularly those containing the *sh2* (shrunken-3 or supersweets) and *se* (sugary enhanced) genes, are particularly susceptible to **imbibitional chilling injury**. Seeds of these sweetcorns are typically low in starch (less food available for germination requirements), high in sugar (susceptible to fungal infection) and brittle (pericarp and endosperm crack easily during rough handling). A rapid uptake of cold water frequently damages the delicate membranes within the seed. If this does not kill the seed directly, fungal infection through the damaged membranes will certainly inhibit germination. Reduce the chances of poor sweetcorn germination by ensuring that seed is handled carefully, that seed is sown accurately and at a suitable depth to prevent fluctuations in moisture availability, and that soil/growing medium temperatures are above 10°C.

Petunias, impatiens and marigolds are the standard lines for bedding plant sales. However, if you are looking to **increase sales potential** in the bedding plant line, consider adding other popular lines. Trends in the USA indicate that dianthus, lobelia, salvia, snapdragons (who can spell antirrhinum anyway?), verbena and vinca are the second-line winners. Local trends suggest the popular lines to choose are lobelia, salvia and snapdragons, although vincas should do extremely well.

Marketing is the theme for the next Seedling Growers' Association (SGASA) symposium. Sutherland Seedlings have discovered a good niche market in their new Retail section at the nursery. Included in this division of the nursery business, is the supply of indigenous and exotic trees for the rapidly expanding market for amenity and garden plantings, shelterbelts and windbreaks, and high value timbers such as sawtooth oak, black wood, pin oak, jacaranda, yellowwoods and wild olive.

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Seedling grown with Osmocote Mini® on the left, the seedling on the right without

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Seedling trays (middle row) grown with Osmocote Mini®

Vegetable plugs grown with Osmocote Mini®

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Cultivar highlights of the Delmas Farmers' Day

STAR 9001 F, Hybrid impressed everyone with its excellent yield, fruit size and quality.

STAR 2001 bean displays outstanding pod quality with a very distinctive glossy green colour imparted by the 'permanent green gene'. Eating quality is second to none.

STAR 5051 a reddish butterhead lettuce variety of excellent quality.

STAR 7702 F, Hybrid supersweet sweetcorn impressed growers with its strong, vigorous plants and top quality ears.

STAR 5056 a top quality green oak-leaf lettuce cultivar.

STAR 3301 F, Hybrid cabbage. A top yielder with excellent standability on the land.

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PRESTASIE BEPROEFTE SAAD OP SY HEEL BESTE

Delmas Vegeta

1

2

4

5

7

8

9

Vegetable Farmers' Day

3

6

1. Gus Köhne welcomes a group of farmers to the Delmas Vegetable Farmers' Day and sets the scene for an interesting and informative tour of the Demonstration Field.
2. Donald Millar-Watt demonstreer die hoogtepunte van Starke Ayres se suikermielie-program, soos die supersoet kultivars **STAR 7701** en **STAR 7702**, aan 'n groep boere.
3. John Herbert spoke on cucurbits and on the new **F₁ Hybrid Pumpkin STAR 7001** in particular and is seen here explaining the advantages of Jupiter Seedless Watermelon.
4. 'n Uitsig van 'n gedeelte van die demonstrasieterrein wat so netjies uitgelê was.
5. Allan MacKinley gesels oor **STAR 1102 F₁** baster-tuinbeet en **STAR 3002 F₁** baster-geelwortel, 'n uitstekende kultivar vir bossies, kratte en sakkies.
6. Darryl Lloyd praat oor Starke Ayres se uitstekende Koolreeks. Die uitstaande kultivars van hierdie jaar was **STAR 3301** kopkool en **STAR 4401** blomkool wat in die somer presteer.
7. Morkel Combrink speaking on eggplant, chillies, peppers and tomatoes. The highlight of his talk was the new **tomato hybrid STAR 9001** with excellent yields and disease resistance. An excellent example of this cultivar's yield capability can be seen on the right of the photograph where leaves have been removed to expose the fruit.
8. A general view of a section of the demonstration grounds showing Starke Ayres newly released range of speciality lettuce cultivars, including **STAR 5052** a red oak-leaf, **STAR 5053** a red leaf, **STAR 5054** a cos and **STAR 5056** a green oakleaf lettuce.
9. Ken Jeanes discussing bush bean cultivars and speciality lettuce cultivars. **STAR 2001** bean was very impressive, its permanent green colour and excellent quality got an extremely enthusiastic response from chain store buyers.

Wood alternatives

Wood is required in large quantities for both building and fuel purposes. Woodlots have been started as a means of reducing the demand for wood from indigenous bush and commercial plantations. Some ancient techniques for non-destructive harvesting of trees should prove effective under local conditions.

Coppice growth is commonly used in commercial forestry using gum trees. To coppice, the tree is felled at a

convenient height and the stump allowed to shoot and form a new trunk. Multiple trunks usually form, which can be thinned if desired. Under strong browsing pressure from animals, the soft coppice growth can be seriously damaged, even to the extent of killing the stump.

A pollard is far more suitable where animals cannot be kept out of the forest. In essence, all the pollard achieves is separation of animals from the soft new

growth. The bolting (trunk from which new shoots will grow) must be high enough that cattle and goats cannot reach the new shoots.

The line drawings give a clear indication of the different techniques, and how they look after harvesting the wood (Rackham, O., 1989. The last forest: the story of Hatfield forest. J.M. Dent & Sons, London). Suitable trees readily available in South Africa would be eucalypts, wattles and leucena species. A number of fruit, nut and indigenous species would also be suitable. Planting trees in hedges or as avenues would use little space, improve the countryside, as well as give a useful harvest at regular intervals.

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Success with Starke Ayres onion cultivars

Frankie Lawrence of Idestone Farms, near Douglas in the Northern Cape, had excellent results with three Starke Ayres short day onion cultivars — **STAR 5501**, **Early Gold** and **Sonic** — during the 1993 season.

Early Gold, the earliest of the three varieties, was direct sown on 4 March 1993 and harvested at 50% leaf drop on 4 October 1993, with a marketable yield of 65t/ha of medium to large bulbs plus 2t/ha of small bulbs.

Sonic F₁ Hybrid was slightly later than the Early Gold, but was also sown later. It was direct sown on 15 March 1993 and harvested at 50% leaf drop on 18 October 1993, with a marketable yield of 63t/ha.

STAR 5501 F₁ Hybrid was direct sown on 19 April 1993 and harvested at 50% leaf drop on 25 October 1993 with a marketable yield of 60t/ha. STAR 5501 is a newly released Granex type onion with improved yields and uniformity.

Radium, grown in the same field, yielded 38t/ha and was also harvested on 25 October 1993 at 50% leaf drop.

All the above cultivars were grown in the same land under a centre pivot on sandy soils. The soil was prepared using a 'Morphy' Ripper (Hammerhead

STAR 5501 F₁ hybrid, a newly released Granex-type onion cultivar shows its yield potential and improved uniformity.

Frankie Lawrence and John Herbert examine the STAR 5501 harvest at Idestone Farms.

Ripper) followed by a Wonder Tiller with a roller. The seed was drilled direct using a Stanhay Belt Planter.

Wheat seed was broadcast at 50kg/ha to protect the onion seedlings from wind damage and sand blasting. The land was then sprayed with Fusilade to kill the wheat once it was 10cm tall.

The land was treated with Totril and Ronstar herbicides at 1 and 1,5 l/ha respectively when the onions were at the 3 to 4 leaf stage.

The crop was sprayed with Dithane and Kocide twice and once with Rovral to control fungal and bacterial diseases. Thrips were also sprayed for when found.

Frankie supplied all his fertiliser through the irrigation water using liquid 3:1:2 (20) fertiliser. This was applied in seven applications, at intervals of about 2 weeks, until 2 July 1993, giving a total of 180 kg Nitrogen, 60 kg Phosphate and 120 kg Potassium per hectare.

Frankie windrowed his onions to dry them and used a potato sorter to size and grade the onions before sending them to the market.

Starke Ayres congratulates Frankie on his successful onion crop and thank him for confirming belief that STAR 5501, Early Gold and Sonic are excellent cultivars, capable of giving high yields of top quality bulbs.

Snippets

Hanging baskets can look very tatty. **Coir Basket Liners** are now available from Starke Ayres to prevent the tatty look of plastic liners. At busy nurseries, the convenience of Coir Basket Liners ensures quick lining and planting of baskets, without the risk of a messy job.

Coir Basket Liners are fully biodegradable. The high lignin content of the fibre, combined with natural rubber latex, results in a long-lived, good-looking liner. Coir Basket Liners offer more than simply convenience, they are cheaper per basket and easier and neater to fit than loose coir.

Remember to add plants into the sides of the baskets. Simply make a slit in the Liner and push the root plugs through into the growing medium.

Palm Peat has received the nod of approval from Alan Meerow, Palm and Tropical Ornamentals Specialist at the Fort Lauderdale Research and Education Centre, University of Florida. He recommends Palm Peat because of its high water holding capacity (equal or superior to sphagnum peat), **excellent drainage**, absence of weeds and pathogens, greater physical resiliency than sphagnum peats, no ecological drawbacks as it is a fully renewable resource, slower decomposition rate during use than either sedge or sphagnum peats, acceptable pH, cation exchange capacity and electrical conductivity levels, and it is much easier to wet than sphagnum peats. As he notes, Palm Peat 'may well be a product of our time'.

Die Instituut vir Groente en Sierplante bied 'n **Tamatiekonferensie** aan op 5 Mei 1994 te Roodeplaat, Pretoria. Die tema van die dag is 'Verhoging van produksie-effektiwiteit'. Die registrasiegeld beloop R195,00 per persoon en sluit middagete, tee, koffie en 'n volledige bundel met lesings in. Tjeks kan uitgemaak word aan: Die Direkteur, Instituut vir groente en Sierplante, en gepos word aan: Tamatiekonferens, Instituut vir groente en Sierplante, Privaatsak X293, Pretoria, 0001.

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TUNNEL TALK

Biological control of insects in cucumber crops in the Netherlands

By Joost van den Eijnden — Nunhems Seeds

The success of biological control depends on many factors. Firstly, the start of the crop has to be clean from insects and from residues. The harmful effect of some chemicals on predators can last for up to 12 weeks after spraying, such as most pyrethroids. Even a pesticide listed as safe for natural enemies can kill up to 25% of those oversprayed.

Secondly, a high relative humidity in

the greenhouse is often necessary for the development of the population of predators. For effective control, it is necessary to monitor the population regularly, using blue and yellow trapboards.

Biological control involves monitoring the population of insects and introducing predators at the right place and time. When necessary, a minimum of pesticides should be used

and then only those which are least harmful to beneficial insects.

Western Flower Thrips (WFT)

Chemical control of WFT is very difficult since only the larvae and adults are susceptible to chemical products, and the adults tend to hide in flowers and other places. DDVP is effective but as it causes fruit abortion in cucumbers, it

Chemical Name	Trade Name	<i>Phytoseiulus persimilis</i>	<i>Encarsia formosa</i>	<i>Amblyseius cucumeris</i>	<i>Orius</i>	<i>Dacnusa and Diglyphus</i>	<i>Aphidoletes</i>
Insecticides/ Acaricides	Apollo	—	—	—	—	—	—
	Applaud	—	—	—	—	—	—
	<i>Bacillus thuringiensis</i>	—	—	—	—	—	—
Cyanid	Calcid	+	+	+	+	+	+
Cyhexatin		x	x	x	—	x	x
Diazinon	Basudine	—	x	x	x	x	x
Fenbutatin-oxide	Torque	—	—	—	—	—	—
Malathion			x	x	x	x	x
Mevinfos		x	x	x	x	x	x
	Niesorum	—	—	—	—	—	—
	Nomolt	—	+	—	x	—	—
Parathion		—	x	x	x	x	x
	Pinmor	—	—	+	—	—	—
Oxamyl	Vydate(to pour)	—	+	+	+	+	+
	Vermitec	+	x	+	x	x	x
Fungicides	AAterra	—	—	—	—	—	—
	Baycor	—	—	—	—	—	—
Benzamidazol		x	—	+	—	—	—
	Curamil	x	x	x	x	x	x
	Daconil	—	—	—	—	—	—
	Eupareen	—	+	x	—	—	+
	Fungaflor	—	—	—	—	—	—
Iprodion	Rovral	—	—	—	—	—	—
Maneb/zineb		—	—	—	—	—	—
	Nimrod	+	—	+	—	—	—
	Previcur N	—	—	—	—	—	—
	Rubigan	—	—	—	—	—	—
	Sumisclex	—	—	—	—	—	—
Thiram		—	—	—	—	—	—
Triforine	Funginex	—	—	+	—	—	—
Sulfur		+	+	+	—	—	—
Vinclozlin	Ronilan	—	—	—	—	—	—

— = safe

+ = acceptable, partly killed

x = harmful

open = effect unknown

products not mentioned, in general, not to be used with biological control

TUNNEL TALK

can only be used at the start (before flowering) and at the end of the crop. Other products are less effective and will harm the predators.

For biological control of thrips, the predators *Amblyseius cucumeris* and *Orius* are used. *Amblyseius* is 0,5 mm in length and has an oval back. After being in the crop for some time, the colour of this predator changes from light pink to dark pink to almost orange. Because *Amblyseius* is originally a soil mite, it prefers to seek and to live in hiding positions on the plant, such as the growing points, flowers and leaf nodes. *Amblyseius* develops best at a relative humidity of 80–85%. *Amblyseius* feeds mainly on the very young thrips larvae and, to a lesser extent, on spider mites.

As this predator can only kill one or two thrips larvae per day, it is important that they are introduced to the crop as early as possible and in very large numbers. In order to ensure a consistently high population, regular re-introduction of *Amblyseius* into the cucumber crop is necessary. It is, therefore, very important to start clean. At the end of the former crop, spray with DDVP 2—3 times with an interval of 5 days. After the old crop is removed, spray the empty greenhouse with DDVP again. Two weeks after planting, the first *Amblyseius* should be introduced, with repeated introductions every 2 weeks. It is not profitable to introduce more *Amblyseius* during the last 5 weeks of the crop.

Another successful WFT parasite is the assassin bug *Orius*. The adult *Orius* bug is 3–4 mm in length and is predominantly black. *Orius* eats all stadia of thrips and can eliminate thrips at five times the rate of *Amblyseius*. The *Orius* population is susceptible to chemical products e.g. Rubigan is

reasonably safe but a product such as Curamil is harmful to the population. *Orius* can be introduced effectively in spots where the first thrips larvae are found.

White Fly

The parasitic wasp *Encarsia formosa* has been successfully used in the control of greenhouse white fly (*Trialeurodes vaporariorum*). The *Encarsia* wasp is about 0.6 mm long with a black head and thorax and a yellow abdomen. The adults kill some white fly by feeding on them. The adult *Encarsia* female usually lays her eggs inside the larvae or 'scales' of the white fly. The developing parasitic grub feeds within the white fly scale, which will turn black within 10 days and after 2–3 weeks, a new wasp emerges.

The introduction of *Encarsia formosa* normally starts preventively and is then introduced 3 to 7 times per crop cycle. The parasitic wasp *Encarsia formosa* is also capable of parasitising the white fly *Bemisia tabaci*.

Lannate, used at the end of the former crop, will have a negative effect on the growth of the *Encarsia* population in the new crop. If Vermitec is used at the start of the new crop, one should delay the introduction of *Encarsia* for two weeks. The life cycle of the white fly is about 3,5 weeks, so if an early infection of white fly arises, part of the population will be missed by *Encarsia*. This can be compensated for by the application of Applaud, which will affect the larvae of white fly, although it is not 100% effective. Alternatives for Applaud are dripping Vydate L or the application of Calcid, both of which are capable of affecting the adult white fly.

Spider Mites

The spider predator *Phytoseiulus persimilis* is used to control spider mites. The adult predators are orange-red in colour, 0,7 mm in length with a bold pear-shaped body. They are fast-moving and slightly larger than the spider mite. The spider predators multiply very rapidly. Optimal conditions for rapid multiplication are temperatures between 22 to 25°C at a relative humidity of 80–85%.

An adult predator can consume about 5 spider mites or 20 eggs per day. In the absence of spider mites, *Phytoseiulus persimilis* survives by cannibalism. The first introduction should occur locally, as soon as the first spider mites are discovered. It is important that frequent checks for the presence of spider mites in the crop be undertaken.

Aphids and Leafminers

Aphids can be effectively controlled by the gallmidge *Aphidoletes aphidimyza*. *Aphidoletes* is about 2,5 mm long and orange in colour. At a temperature of 20°C, the life cycle will be approximately three weeks. *Aphidoletes* lays her eggs near colonies of Aphids, the larvae thus feeding on the Aphids.

Effective treatment of leafminers is possible through the use of the wasps *Dacnusa siberica* and *Diglyphus isaea*. *Dacnusa* is about 3 mm in length, has long antennae and is black in colour. *Diglyphus* is a wasp with a length of 2 mm and short antennae.

N.B.: The chemicals mentioned above may not be registered in South Africa and growers are advised to check with chemical companies whether their use is legal.

Quality space

Giving plants a little extra space can sometimes give startling results. The main objective of allowing more space between plants would be to improve plant quality, particularly of potted landscape plants.

Most nurseries have potted plants spaced simply according to the size of the pots. For larger specimens, this results in tall, thin plants, unable to support themselves once the support of their neighbours has been removed. Plants with spindly trunks are much more susceptible to damage during handling.

Seedling nurseries have less scope for plant spacing, being limited to the range of seedling trays available.

However, even here the tray model can be chosen to suit the shape of seedling. Spacing trays apart on the nursery tables can also have a dramatic effect on diseases, particularly reducing the incidence of *Botrytis* in susceptible seedlings.

To produce quality plants requires a higher degree of care. Simply spacing plants more can be a simple means of dramatically improving plant quality.

Improved potted plant quality is possible simply by spacing the plants correctly. Sutherland Seedlings have neatly resolved the spacing problem, as well as the tendency for plants in bags to fall over by placing the bags between concrete pots.

Precision sowing for profit

Accuracy in sowing seed into Speedling trays has a major impact on profitability. The object is clearly to grow only full trays of seedlings. Two different methods are generally used to achieve this. Which one is best will differ according to individual circumstances.

The shotgun approach involves sowing a number of seeds into each cavity. Once germination has occurred, excess seedlings are thinned and discarded, or pricked into empty cells. While the initial sowing process is easy, a large labour force is needed to thin seedlings after germination. This method is generally used where less accurate sowing methods are used, particularly machines lacking an accurate singulation method; where labour is relatively cheap; and where seed lots are of poor vigour and cannot be improved by screening or pre-germination.

Disadvantages of the shotgun method are largely related to the expense of having to thin seedlings in the nursery. Apart from the direct expense of thinning, indirect expenses such as that caused by damage to remaining seedlings are difficult to estimate. Where good quality seed is

Germination temperatures are critical in a seedling nursery. Even relatively short periods of high temperature can have a devastating effect on number of effective seedlings. Here, cabbage seed sown in summer shows the effect of too high temperature during germination. Low vigour seed germinates in the same manner.

used, the shotgun method of sowing represents a straight waste of seed.

Precision sowing contrasts with the shotgun approach by aiming to sow a single, viable seed into each cavity. The sowing process must be carefully monitored, with particular care taken to set the machine correctly to obtain accurate singulation and placement of the seed. Ability to sow pre-germinated seed is particularly important in this

approach provided ungerminated and non-viable seed is removed before sowing.

The importance of aiming for a seedling in each cell is illustrated by the effect of relatively minor losses per tray on the total capacity of a nursery. A mere five cells not sown in a 200-cell tray represents a further 2.5% loss between nursery capacity and seedlings sold.

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New Products Update

STAR 4403 is 'n hoë potensiaal F₁ baster blomkool wat in Januarie 1993 vrygestel is. Groot regop plante met groot koppe van 'n uitstekende gehalte en goeie verdraagsaamheid teen koue toestande is die kenmerke van hierdie ipwindende kultivar. 'n Puik spanmaat vir **STAR 4401** vir someroes en **STAR 4402** vir herfs tot vroeë winter oes.

STAR 5501 F₁ 'n Baster kort-dag uiekultivar wat met groot sukses in 1993 vrygestel is en in sekere gebiede geen voorstelling meer nodig het nie. Granex-tipe ui met 'n goue-bruin kleur en 'n bolvorm wat wissel can effens plat Granex to Grano. Meer eenvormige bolgrootte as die meeste Granex kultivars. Verdraagsaam vir Piekwortel. Beste saaitye Maart–April. Gereed vir oes gedurende September–Oktober.

STAR 1102 F₁ Uiteindelik 'n baster tuinbeet kultivar met al die eienskappe wat ons al solank soek. Top opbrengs, egal; ige bolle met 'n aantreklike voorkoms en uitstekende interne kleur en gehalte. Goeie verdraagsaamheid teen koue toestande. Aantreklike medium lengte blare. Beskikbaar vir herfs 1994.

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